

Adsorption, desorption and kinetics of sorption of nickel on four different soil types of India

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Abstract : Nickel is one of the heavy metals exhibited greater migration properties which is frequently found in contaminated soil and ground water. The concentration of heavy metals in soil depends largely on sorption and desorption reaction on the surface of soil particles. So the objective of this work is to find out the adsorption, desorption and kinetics of sorption of nickel on four typical profile samples of different soil types of India. In all the studies the analysis of nickel ions was done using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, and the results were statistically analysed. Interpretation of results showed that the adsorption capacity of soil is closely related to the physico-chemical properties of soil such as organic matter, clay content, exchangeable cations and pH. The Freundlich adsorption isotherm was found to be better fit than Langmuir adsorption isotherm with respect to nickel adsorption. The Freundlich and Langmuir parameters were closely related to the difference in the nickel adsorption characteristics of soils. The desorption of nickel was rapid during the initial two extractions (more than 70%). Forest soil and laterite soil retained some fractions of adsorbed nickel even after eight successive extractions which shows the high sorption characteristics of these soils. The rate of adsorption of nickel was proportional to the concentration of nickel remaining unadsorbed at a given time irrespective of their initial concentration which indicated invariably their agreement with first order kinetics.

Keywords : Adsorption, desorption, kinetics of sorption, nickel.

Introduction

In trace amounts, nickel is an essential element for both animals and plants. However, at higher concentration all nickel compounds are found toxic^{1,2}. Widespread industrial applications and high mobility³ are two primary reasons why nickel is frequently found in contaminated soil and ground water. Another reason for the presence of nickel in soil is due to solid urban wastes. The concentration of heavy metals in soil is most likely controlled by sorption and desorption reaction on the surface of soil particles. High concentration of heavy metals especially nickel was reported in the soil of Kerala⁴ and rivers of Kerala⁵. So the present investigation aims to study the adsorption, desorption and kinetics of sorption of nickel on four different soil types of India, so as to

analyse the bioavailability and hence the toxicity problems.

Results and discussion

Four different soil types of India were selected for the present study. Physico-chemical properties of soils were determined and are summarized in Tabel 1. The adsorption of nickel by all the four soils clearly indicated that the sorption was almost linear upto maximum concentration for all the soils (Table 2). This may be due to more metal ions might be available for sorption at higher concentration and hence the chances of getting into exchange complex is greater⁶.

Forest soil recorded high adsorption of nickel followed by alluvial and laterite soil, the lowest adsorption was

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of soils

Properties	Soils			
	Laterite	Alluvial	Forest	Red Sandy loam
Mechanical composition				
(a) Clay %	30.36	31.6	39.80	21.20
(b) Silt %	2.60	7.50	11.50	3.60
(c) Fine sand %	30.62	22.90	18.40	26.60
(d) Coarse sand %	36.42	38.00	30.30	48.60
pH (1 : 2.5)	5.19	5.60	5.90	4.90
Organic carbon %	2.00	1.80	3.20	0.60
Cation exchange capacity (mg/100 g)	9.80	10.10	12.6	3.50
Exchangeable Cations (mg/100 g)				
(a) Magnesium	0.44	0.21	0.51	0.12
(b) Calcium	0.87	0.32	1.11	0.28
(c) Potassium	0.06	0.09	0.13	0.15
(d) Sodium	0.08	0.10	0.11	0.08

sented in Table 3 shows that the data was best fitted to Freundlich adsorption equation than Langmuir adsorption equation since it was significant upto 95 to 99%.

From the Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms various constants and coefficients were computed and summarized in Table 4, which shows that Langmuir adsorption maximum (V_m) was highest for forest soil (1428 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Intermediate values was shown by alluvial soil (909 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and laterite soil (833 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Low value was shown by red sandy loam (714 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Adsorption maxima is a measure of continuous adsorbate molecule supplying power to the plants. Adsorption maxima are correlated with soil clay and carbonate contents, CEC and exchangeable cations¹². The high adsorption maxima for forest soil may be due to its high organic matter, clay content and exchangeable cations compared to other soils (Table 1).

Table 2. Adsorption of nickel by different soils (means)

C_0 ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Laterite soil		Alluvial soil		Forest soil		Red Sandy loam	
	x/m ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	C ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)						
125	115.80	1.83	110.9	2.812	116.80	1.64	58.95	13.25
250	200.95	9.81	208.7	8.26	224.39	5.121	131.80	23.64
500	391.44	21.71	390.5	21.90	428.78	14.24	305.30	38.92
1000	639.99	72.02	678.1	64.38	855.05	28.98	618.30	77.24

C_0 : Initial concentration, x/m : Amount of nickel adsorbed, C : Equilibrium concentration.

noticed in the case of red sandy loam (Table 2). The high sorption characteristics of nickel on forest soil is due to its high humus content, clay content⁷ and pH of soil^{8,9} since there is a close relation between nickel sorption with clay and humus contents of soil. The adsorption data of nickel recorded for different soils were fitted to two adsorption equations viz. Langmuir and Freundlich equations. Table 3 shows that adsorption data for all the soils gave almost a linear fit with two adsorption equations^{10,11}. However when the correlation coefficient (r^2) between the parameter in respect of each isotherm was tested statistically, shows varying magnitude of r^2 values which decide the best fit isotherm. Both the equations gave positive test for all the soils under study. The r^2 values pre-

Table 3. Correlation coefficient (r^2) of the Langmuir and Freundlich constants with the adsorption of nickel

Soils	r^2	
	Langmuir equation	Freundlich equation
Laterite	0.942 ^a	0.9757 ^a
Alluvial	0.976 ^a	0.9981 ^b
Forest	0.773 (NS)	0.9868 ^a
Red Sandy loam	0.644 (NS)	0.9691 ^a

^aSignificant at 5% level. ^bSignificant at 1% level. NS : Not significant.

Laterite soil showed high bonding energy (b) which being a measure of relative affinity of nickel to the adsorbate (0.0468 ml/ μg). Thus the release of nickel would be relatively low in this soil. Red sandy loam showed low bonding energy constant (0.006 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) compared to other soils.

Table 4. Langmuir and Freundlich constants and coefficients for the adsorption of nickel by different soils

Soils	Langmuir isotherm parameters		Maximum buffer capacity $V_m \times b$	Freundlich isotherm parameters	
	Adsorption maximum V_m ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Bonding energy b ($\text{ml}/\mu\text{g}$)		$1/n$	Distribution coefficient k ($\text{ml}/\mu\text{g}$)
	Laterite	833 ^a		0.0468	38.99
Alluvial	909 ^a	0.0393	35.71	0.584 ^b	61.30
Forest	1428 (NS)	0.0395	56.42	0.679 ^a	78.45
Red Sandy loam	714 (NS)	0.0060	4.61	1.501 ^a	1.03

^aSignificant at 5% level. ^bSignificant at 1% level. NS : Not significant.

The maximum buffer capacity being a measure of capacity of soil to retain the adsorbed nickel was relatively high in the case of forest soil (56.42). This further supports the capacity of forest soil to retain more nickel in strongly adsorbed form. Red sandy loam recorded relatively low maximum buffer capacity (4.61) which may be due to its low content of clay and organic matter.

Using Freundlich adsorption isotherm, distribution coefficient k and $1/n$ were determined, which also explain the sorption character of nickel in soils. In the present study laterite and forest soil had been shown high value of distribution coefficient (81.37 ml/ μg and 78.45 ml/ μg) which reflects the high retention of applied nickel in the soil, since the distribution coefficient k appears to be a good index of the relative metal sorption affinities of soil¹³. Red sandy loam showed lowest value of distribution coefficient (1.03 ml/ μg). The magnitude of the constant $1/n$ being the slope of isotherm showed almost a reverse pattern of k (Table 4). The difference in value of Freundlich adsorption parameters k and $1/n$ arise due to the difference in organic matter content and soil texture (Table 1). Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption parameters mentioned above clearly indicated that forest soil would retain fairly large amount of applied nickel in strongly bonded form

which may not be readily released to plants or for pollution of ground water. On the other hand red sandy loam may not retain high amount of applied nickel in strongly adsorbed form, thus easily released into soil solution. Laterite and alluvial soil behaved intermediary. The difference in sorption characters of different soils is closely related to its physico-chemical characters such as organic matter content, clay content, exchangeable cations and pH.

Desorption studies of nickel shows that the desorbed nickel on eight successive extractions varies from soil to soil (Table 5). The percentage of nickel desorbed at each fraction for different soils has been shown in Fig. 1. In red sandy loam a rapid release of nickel (75.1%) was noticed in the first extraction. The red sandy loam released almost all the adsorbed nickel after eight successive extractions. This may be due to low clay and organic matter content of the soil. However forest soil and laterite soil retained some fraction of adsorbed nickel even after eight successive extractions. This may primarily due to high organic matter and high amount of clay minerals of these soils which retained the sorbed nickel. Alluvial soil behaved intermediary. The different desorption pattern shown by different soils may be due to its variation

Table 5. Successive desorption of nickel from soils ($\mu\text{g/g}$)

Soils	Number of extractions								Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
Laterite	102.6	53.4	34.1	21.2	12.2	11.5	9.2	8.2	252.44
Alluvial	152.6	57.0	32.6	16.0	10.1	7.2	4.1	2.8	282.41
Forest	140.0	62.4	35.8	19.0	16.2	9.1	8.2	6.1	296.8
Red Sandy loam	198.5	48.6	9.4	3.9	1.09	1.0	0.8	0.8	264.12

Fig. 1. The percentage of desorption of nickel against the number of extraction in different soils.

in nature, amount of colloidal materials, organic matter content and pH (Table 1).

Kinetic study of nickel sorption reveals that forest soil showed highest sorption at any given period of time followed by that of laterite and alluvial soils while red sandy loam showed least sorption at any given time compared to other soils (Table 6). In all the soils adsorption of nickel steadily increased with progress of time upto 160 min. The magnitude of adsorption varied with soils depending upon the amount and nature of clay content and organic matters as well as concentration of nickel ions and competing cations in the soils^{14,15}.

The amount of nickel sorbed (C_s) when plotted against square root of time \sqrt{t} straight lines was observed for all the soils under the present studies. The kinetic parameters a (intercept) and b (slope) computed from the graph were found to be statistically significant at 5% level (Table 7). The parameter ' a ' indicates the nickel retention capacity of the soil. The highest value of ' a ' was shown by forest soil followed by that of laterite, alluvial and red sandy loam soils (Table 7). The parameter b or $dC_s/d\sqrt{t}$ indicates the overall rate of adsorption pooled over different time intervals as well as among different soils at different time intervals was calculated by substituting the value of $dC_s/d\sqrt{t}$ in the rate equation. The data summarized in Table 8 indicated that the rate of adsorption varied from soil to soil and it decreased with progress of time for all the four soils. This is mainly because of progressive saturation of ion exchange sites in all soil matrices. The initial nickel sorption kinetics was rapid on soil in all the pH values¹⁶. At any given time the rate of adsorption of nickel was found to be high in forest soil followed by laterite and alluvial soil where as it was low

Table 6. Kinetics of nickel adsorption in different coconut growing soils (means)

Time ' t ' in min	Laterite soil		Alluvial soil		Forest soil		Red Sandy loam	
	C_s ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	C_1 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)						
10	73.0	5.20	70.9	5.41	75.4	4.95	37.9	8.71
20	78.5	4.65	75.3	4.97	80.1	4.48	41.2	8.38
40	84.8	4.02	81.0	4.40	86.4	3.85	44.6	8.04
80	90.0	3.50	85.5	3.95	93.0	3.20	48.8	7.62
160	94.9	3.01	92.0	3.30	97.0	2.80	53.9	7.11

C_s – Amount of nickel adsorbed. C_1 – Amount of nickel in the equilibrium solution.

Table 7. Parameters for the kinetics of nickel adsorption in the soils

Soils	<i>a</i> ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	<i>b</i> or dC_s/dt ($\mu\text{g/g}/\text{min}$)
Laterite	68.2 ^a	2.24
Alluvial	65.5 ^a	2.16
Forest	70.2 ^a	2.27
Red Sandy loam	33.5 ^a	1.65

^aSingnificant at 5% level.

Table 8. Rate of adsorption of nickel in different soils ($\mu\text{g/g}/\text{min}$)

Time 't' in min	Soils			
	Laterite	Alluvial	Forest	Red Sandy loam
10	0.3550	0.3429	0.3603	0.2615
20	0.2514	0.2425	0.2547	0.1849
40	0.1778	0.1714	0.1801	0.1307
80	0.1257	0.1212	0.1273	0.0924
160	0.0880	0.0856	0.0900	0.0653

in the case of red sandy loam. This character of soil depends upon the availability of organic and inorganic colloidal materials and pH. Plotting the rate of nickel adsorption dC_s/dt against the concentration of nickel in the equilibrium solution (C_t) gave straight lines (Fig. 2) for all the four soils. This further suggests that the rate of nickel adsorption was proportional to the concentration of nickel remaining unadsorbed at any given time, irrespective of its initial concentration.

Thus the nickel adsorption kinetics in the present investigation obeyed a first order reaction kinetics. First order kinetics of sorption of nickel was already reported¹⁷. First order kinetics of sorption was also reported for heavy metals such as cadmium on activated carbon¹⁸ and chromium on alma dust¹⁹.

Experimental

Four typical profile soil samples (0–90 cm) of different soil types of India (Kerala in southern India) were used in the present investigation (Laterite soil of Kasaragod, Alluvial soil of Kannur, Forest soil of Wyanad, Red Sandy loam of Kasaragod). The physico-chemical properties of all the soils were determined. Stock solution of Ni^{2+} ion were prepared by dissolving A.R. Nickel

Fig. 2. Dependence of the rate of nickel adsorption on the soils on the concentration of nickel remaining in solution.

nitrate in distilled water giving a concentration of 1000 ppm as Ni^{2+} ion.

The nickel adsorption was studied by batch equilibration method. Five gram soil samples were weighed into series of 50 cm^3 polythene centrifuge tubes and 25 ml solutions containing 25, 50, 100 and 200 ppm, Ni^{2+} (as nickel nitrate) were added separately. The experiment was done in five replications. The mixture was shaken for 48 h, after which it was centrifuged. Unadsorbed por-

tion of nickel was determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC-Avanta). From the data the quantity of nickel adsorbed by soil was computed²⁰. The data were fitted to the following two equations describing the adsorption progress i.e. Langmuir equation²¹ and Freundlich equation²².

Langmuir equation :

$$\frac{c}{x/m} = \frac{c}{V_m} + \frac{1}{bV_m}$$

Freundlich equation :

$$x/m = kC^{1/n}$$

where C = the equilibrium concentration of nickel in $\mu\text{g/ml}$, x/m = the amount of nickel adsorbed per unit amount of soil in $\mu\text{g/g}$, k = the distribution co-efficient in $\text{ml}/\mu\text{g}$, b = the constant related to the bonding energy in $\text{ml}/\mu\text{g}$ and n = empirical constant (dimensionless).

Out of the two isotherms the best fit adsorption data corresponding to each soil was tested statistically by employing least square techniques²³. The various constants and co-efficients were also calculated from both the isotherms. Using the co-efficients of Langmuir adsorption the maximum buffer capacity $V_m \times b$ was calculated²⁴.

In the desorption isotherm studies, 5 g each of soils (in five replications) was saturated separately with 200 ppm nickel were subjected to successive desorption for eight times using DTPA solutions after removing unadsorbed fractions. The successively separated solutions was estimated using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC-Avanta). From the data the percentage of desorption was computed for each soil.

For the study of kinetics of nickel adsorption 2.5 g lots of the soil samples in 50 cm^{-1} polythene bottles were charged separately with 25 ml solutions of 25 μg nickel per ml. The experiment was done in five replications and the solutions were centrifuged at the elapse of 10, 20, 40, 80 and 160 min after intermittent shaking. The unadsorbed nickel at different time interval was estimated separately using Atomic Adsorption Spectrophotometer (GBC-Avanta). The adsorbed portion of nickel can be computed from the unadsorbed portion of nickel for each soil. The data was fitted in two sets of format viz. the amount of nickel adsorbed (C_s) versus square root of

time t and the rate of adsorption dC_s/dt versus the concentration of nickel in the equilibrium solution (C_1). In the formats the co-efficient of adsorption were tested by least square techniques. The first format was intended for computing the slope ($dC_s/d\sqrt{t}$) from which the rate of adsorption (dC_s/dt) was calculated using the formula

$$\left[\frac{dC_s}{dt} \right]_t = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t}} \left[\frac{dC_s}{d\sqrt{t}} \right]_t$$

$$\left[\frac{dC_s}{dt} \right]_t \text{ stands for rate of adsorption.}$$

The rate of adsorption was further plotted against the concentration of nickel in the equilibrium solution C_1 to test whether the adsorption process obeyed first order kinetics.

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